

What Questions Can I Ask?

A Taxonomy and Question Catalog for Process Mining Analysis Questions

- Appendix -

Authors: Lisa Zimmermann, Francesca Zerbato, Victoria Gentile, Manuel Resinas, Barbara Weber

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3 Method - Appendix

In the paper, this section outlines the approach to collecting process mining analysis questions and designing the taxonomy. In this document, we provide the following supplementary material:

1. Question Collection 2 – Participant Details P. 2
2. Question Collection 2 – Questionnaire P. 3
3. Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations P. 4
4. Evaluation I – Questionnaire P. 11
5. Evaluation I – Participant Details P. 19

6 Evaluation - Appendix

In the paper, this section outlines the ex-post evaluation we conducted to evaluate the usefulness of the taxonomy and question bank. In this document, we provide the following supplementary material:

1. Process Mining Question Forge – Tool Interface P. 20
2. Evaluation II – Guide P. 23
3. Evaluation II – Questionnaire P. 25
4. Evaluation III – Questionnaire P. 29
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7 Discussion - Appendix

In the paper, this section outlines the interpretation of our findings, its scientific contribution, and discusses its practical implications. In this document, we provide the following supplementary material:

1. ChatGPT Prompt P. 41

Question Collection 2 - Participant Details

ID	Gender	Country	Industry	Position	Expertise	#Years	#Logs	#Projects
P1	Female	Germany	Academic	Researcher	Advanced	3	>15	N/A
P2	Female	Switzerland	Academic	Researcher	Average	2	3-5	N/A
P3	Male	Germany	Banking	Process Analyst	Basic	1	>15	N/A
P4	Male	Germany	Building Materials	Process Analyst	Advanced	2	3-5	3-5
P5	Female	Germany	Telecommunications	Data Engineer	Basic	1	1-2	1-2
P6	Female	Spain	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Basic	<1	3-5	1-2
P7	Male	Belgium	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Good	1	3-5	3-5
P8	Male	Switzerland	Other	Process Analyst	Advanced	8	>15	>15
P9	Male	Switzerland	Computer Software / Engineering	Consultant	Good	2	10-15	1-2
P10	Male	Germany	Logistics/Procurement	Process Analyst	Advanced	3	>15	3-5
P11	Female	Poland	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Good	2	10-15	3-5
P12	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Data Engineer	Advanced	2	6-9	3-5
P13	Male	Switzerland	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Good	3	6-9	1-2
P14	Male	Switzerland	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Good	2	3-5	1-2
P15	Female	Netherlands	Management Consulting	Consultant	Good	4	>15	>15
P16	Male	Portugal	Food/Beverages	Process Analyst	Average	1	0	1-2
P17	Male	Austria	Consumer Goods	Data Engineer	Good	2	6-9	6-9
P18	Female	Germany	Computer Software/Engineering	Data Engineer	Advanced	6	>15	6-9
P19	Male	United Kingdom	Management Consulting	Consultant	Advanced	2	6-9	6-9
P20	Male	Germany	Pharmaceuticals	Process Mining Expert / SME	Advanced	5	3-5	3-5
P21	Male	Germany	Logistics/Procurement	Process Analyst	Good	4	6-9	6-9
P22	Male	Spain	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Average	<1	1-2	1-2
P23	Male	Spain	Computer Software/Engineering	Consultant	Advanced	1	>15	>15
P24	Male	Germany	Food Production	Process Analyst	Advanced	4	1-2	3-5
P25	Male	Estonia	Academic	Researcher	Advanced	>10	>15	>15
P26	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Advanced	1	>15	>15
P27	Male	France	Computer Networking	Data Scientist	Good	10	3-5	1-2
P28	Male	Switzerland	Management Consulting	Process Analyst	Advanced	>10	>15	>15
P29	Male	Paraguay	Computer Software/Engineering	Data Scientist	Good	>10	3-5	1-2
P30	Female	Netherlands	Academic	Researcher	Good	6	3-5	3-5
P31	Male	Germany	Transportation	Consultant	Good	3	>15	>15
P32	Female	Denmark	Mechanical or Industrial Engineering	Process Analyst	Average	2	1-2	3-5
P33	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Researcher	Advanced	5	10-15	10-15
P34	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Consultant	Basic	1	1-2	1-2
P35	Male	Netherlands	Financial Services	Process Analyst	Good	5	>15	1-2
P36	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Process Analyst	Advanced	6	>15	10-15
P37	Male	Germany	Information Technology/IT	Data Engineer	Average	1	1-2	1-2
P38	Male	Italy	Academic	Professor	Average	6	3-5	1-2
P39	Female	France	Computer Software/Engineering	Developer / Advocate for Process Analytics	Advanced	8	6-9	3-5

Table 1: Participants of Online Survey – Question Collection 2. We provide the participants’ **ID**, their **Gender**, **Country** of residence, the **Industry** of their employment at the time of the data collection, their job title (**Position**), their self rated **Expertise** in process mining, their years of experience with process mining (**# Years**), the number of event logs they have analyzed (**# Logs**), and the number of process mining projects (**# Projects**) they conducted.

Question Collection 2 – Questionnaire

ID	Question	Question Type
1. Demographics		
1.1	What is your gender?	Single choice
1.2	Which country do you currently live in?	Single choice
1.3	Which industry do you currently work in?	Single choice
1.4	What best describes your current position?	Single choice
2. Expertise in PM		
2.1	How would you rate your expertise in the process mining field?	Likert scale
2.2	How many years of experience do you have in the process mining field?	Single choice
2.3	How many event logs have you created and/or analyzed in the last 2 years?	Single choice
2.4	How many process mining projects have you been part of in the last 2 years?	Single choice
3. Projects (repeated up to 3 times, based on answer to 3.7)		
3.1	What process was analyzed?	Open
3.2	Which industry was the analysis conducted for?	Open
3.3	Where did the event log come from?	Single choice
3.4	What was (were) the main goal(s) of the analysis?	Open
3.5	Question-Technique-Pairs for up to 5 questions	
	a. What are the five main questions that were posed for the process mining analysis?	Open
	b. Which techniques were used to answer them?	Single choice
3.6	Question-Technique-Pairs for hypothetical questions	
	a. With hindsight, which additional question(s) could you have come up with that would have been interesting to answer?	Open
	b. Which technique(s) could have been used to answer this (these) additional question(s)?	Open
3.7	Can you recall another recent process mining project that you worked on and would like to share?	Single choice
4. Frequent Questions		
4.1	What are the three most frequent questions you have posed across all your process mining projects?	Open
4.2	Would you like to leave any additional comment?	Open

Table 2: Questionnaire Design Online Survey – Question Collection 2.

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 1 (E2C)

The initial version of the taxonomy was designed based on an empirical-to-conceptual development cycle (Nickerson et al., 2013). We analyzed the questions collected during Question Collection 1 by following grounded theory coding (Charmaz, 2006). First, we used inductive in-vivo coding and afterward identified relations and groups in the focused coding phase. In the focused coding phase, synonym codes were merged, and codes with a frequency lower than two were considered insignificant. Subsequently, different levels of granularity were observed, and the codes were grouped accordingly into more conceptual dimensions, categories, and sub-categories.

Dimensions		Categories & Subcategories						
Question Goal	Optimization	Automation	Transparency	Insights	Monitoring			
Question Perspective	Behavior Transition Change Rework Ping Pong Rule Variants	Organization Organizational structure Roles Relationships	Time Duration Throughput time Evolution Time constraint Frequency Likelihood	Compliance Deviation Duplicate	Performance Bottleneck Change	Function	Data	
Question Type	Descriptive	Explanatory	Quantitative	Comparative	Superlative	Relational Correlation Root Cause	Predictive	Recommendatory

As expected, the first iteration did not meet the objective ending criteria but *Uniqueness* (C). However, the contribution of the first cycle was twofold. First, it confirmed the meta-characteristic. Indeed, all dimensions consisted of structural or contextual building blocks of a question. Second, as Charmaz (2006) argues, coding represents the initial step in advancing from concrete statements within the data to more abstract, analytical interpretations. Therefore, it established a direction for subsequent iterations.

Example: In-Vivo Coding

How is the **throughput time** of the invoicing process **affected** by different **process characteristics**?

In-Vivo Codes: How, Throughput Time, Affected, Process Characteristics

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 2 (C2E)

In the second iteration, we conducted a conceptual-to-empirical development cycle (Nickerson et al., 2013). Based on the meta-characteristic and guided by the dimensions and categories defined in the first iteration, existing foundations were identified in the literature. In particular, we identified and included the *Process Mining Types* (van der Aalst, 2022), *Process Perspectives* (Mannhard, 2018), and the *interrogative word* (Pomerantz, 2005).

As a result, five dimensions and their categories were conceptualized: Question Goal, Question Perspective, Expected Analysis Outcome, Question Formulation, and Envisioned Analysis Step. The process mining analysis questions were then examined for these characteristics.

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories										
Question Goal	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Automation	Improvement	Prediction				
Question Perspective	Control-Flow		Time		Resources			Data			
Question Type	Descriptive		Explanatory		Normative			Predictive			
Expected Analysis Outcome	Number Calculation	Ranking	Relation Cause-Effect Relation Correlation	Potential Automation Potential Improvement Potential	Rule Decision Rule Business Rule	Pattern	Bottleneck	Lead Time	Conformance Check	Difference	
Envisioned Analysis Step	Filtered By Group By Event By Event Sequence By Temporal Constraint				Grouped By Attribute By Event By Event Sequence			Clustered			

Although the identified dimensions and their categories remained unique (C), other ending conditions were not satisfied. A majority of questions exhibited more than one characteristic, especially within the dimension *Envisioned Analysis Step*, which contradicted mutual exclusivity (A). Consequently, this dimension was determined unsuitable for the present taxonomy and dropped for further iterations.

van der Aalst WM (2018) Process discovery from event data: Relating models and logs through abstractions. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 8(3)

Mannhardt F (2018) Multi-perspective process mining. PhD thesis, Mathematics and Computer Science

Nickerson R, Varshney U, Muntermann J (2013) A method for taxonomy development and its application in information systems. European Journal of Information Systems 22(3):336–359, 10.1057/ejis.2012.26

Pomerantz J (2005) A linguistic analysis of question taxonomies. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology 56(7):715–728, 10.1002/asi.20162

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 3 (E2C)

To better inform the taxonomy development, and to be able to identify more universal dimensions, we conducted Question Collection 2 and proceeded with another empirical-to-conceptual development cycle (Nickerson et al., 2013). This time, the aim was to use the newly identified subset of process mining analysis questions to develop and delineate the categories of each dimension, thus refining the taxonomy. The questions collected from the survey were classified in the preliminary taxonomy using an abductive coding approach (Vila-Henninger et al., 2022). On the one hand, the categories and sub-categories defined in the previous iterations were employed as pre-determined deductive codes. As suggested by Braun et al. (2021), the code selection was interpretative and informed by additional contextual information provided by the survey participants, such as the analysis goals and techniques. On the other hand, new inductive in-vivo codes were elaborated when a question did not fit any existing categories for a dimension.

Dimensions		Categories & Subcategories									
Question Goal	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Automation	Improvement	Prediction				
Question Perspective	Control-Flow	Time	Resources	Data	Cost	Undefined					
Question Formulation	Specific	Descriptive	Explanatory	Exploratory	Confirmatory						
Expected Analysis Outcome	Number Calculation Count Frequency Percentage Amount	Ranking	Relation Cause-Effect Relation Correlation	Potential Automation Potential Improvement Potential	Rule Decision Rule Business Rule	Pattern Process Model Normative Path Variant Sequence	Loop Rework Ping Pong	Bottleneck	Lead Time	Conformance Check	Difference
	Evaluation	Recommendation	Circumstances	New Insights	Duration	Temporal Distribution	Resource-related outcomes Organizational Structure Resource Allocation Social Network Roles	Outlier	Benchmarking	Change	Prediction

Example:

What are the additional **costs** that are **produced by late** payments?

Deductive Codes: Descriptive, Cause-Effect Relation, Performance

Inductive Codes: Cost

Classification: Goal: Performance; Perspective: Cost; Formulation: Descriptive; Expected Analysis Outcome: Casual Relation

During this iteration, no new dimensions were identified, but several categories and sub-categories were added based on novel concepts identified in the questions. As a result, all questions could be classified in at least one category in each dimension and we reached *Collective Exhaustiveness* (C) and kept *Uniqueness* (D).

Braun V, Clarke V, Boulton E, Davey L, McEvoy C (2021) The online survey as a qualitative research tool. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* 24(6):641–654, 10.1080/13645579.2020.1805550

Nickerson R, Varshney U, Muntermann J (2013) A method for taxonomy development and its application in information systems. *European Journal of Information Systems* 22(3):336–359, 10.1057/ejis.2012.26

Vila-Henninger L, Dupuy C, van Ingelgom V, Caprioli M, Teuber F, Pennetreau D, Bussi M, Le Gall C. (2022) Abductive coding: theory building and qualitative (re)analysis. *Sociological Methods & Research*:1-34, 10.1177/00491241211067508

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 4 (C2E)

As several new categories were added in the previous iteration, within iteration four, we aimed to adjust and review the taxonomy, following a conceptual-to-empirical approach (Nickerson et al., 2013). Kundisch et al. (2021), distinguish primary operations to revise a taxonomy. In this iteration, the categories and sub-categories were reorganized through merging, renaming, promoting, and demoting. This especially affected the dimension *Expected Primary Outcome*, for which we aimed to reach *Mutual Exclusivity (A)*. After that, all questions of our collection were examined and classified under the revised taxonomy.

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories					
Goal	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction	Action Automation Improvement
Question Perspective	Control-Flow	Time	Resources	Data	Cost	Undefined
Question Formulation	Specific	Descriptive	Explanatory	Exploratory	Confirmatory	
Expected Primary Outcome	Quantifiable Characteristic	Relation	Activity Pattern	Comparison	Evaluation	Prediction
	Count	Causal Relation	Process Structure	Ranking	Assessment	Predictive Model
	Frequency	Correlation	Dominant Behavior	Difference	Recommendation	Simulation Model
	Ratio	Resource-based	Variant	Change	New Insight	
	Amount	Other Relation	Rule	Benchmarking		
Cycle Time		Rework	Deviation			
Distribution		Bottleneck				

In this iteration, we could confirm all objective ending conditions. As no new dimensions or categories were added, we also complied with the ending condition of saturation (D), allowing us to approach the subjective ending conditions. Based on an extensive assessment of the taxonomy as well as the review of several examples by at least three authors, *Robustness (E)* and *Comprehensiveness (H)* were assessed as fulfilled, while *Conciseness (F)*, *Explantoriness (G)*, and *Extensibility (I)*, were deemed unsatisfied due to concerns regarding the expected primary outcome, where we still observed conceptual overlaps.

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 5 (C2E)

In iteration five, another conceptual-to-empirical iteration was carried out (Nickerson et al., 2013). We reflected on the existing dimensions and categories to enhance the taxonomy, particularly in the context of the open subjective ending conditions. To achieve a more concise version of the taxonomy, we decided to merge the dimensions *Question Perspective* and *Expected Primary Outcome*. It allowed us to streamline the latter dimension and eliminate dependencies between the two dimensions.

During the process, we identified that several categories from *Expected Primary Outcome* remained independent of a particular perspective. This observation led us to create a new dimension called *Purpose*. Furthermore, we integrated fundamental concepts from information systems research, specifically the *Taxonomy of Theories* (Gregor, 2006), into the description of the dimension *Question Formulation*. As a result, we redefined this dimension to align with the *primary goal* of the question. We extended Gregor's categories to include the aspect of "Confirmation," recognizing that questions, unlike theories, might aim to confirm an explicit hypothesis held by the questioner.

Through extensive discussions among the authors, we identified two additional dimensions that are relevant components of a process mining question and enhance the explanatory (G) power of the taxonomy. The first is *Context*, which addresses whether a question is specific to a particular domain, utilizing domain-specific language and referring to aspects pertinent only to a specific process. The second new dimension is the *Data Level*, is inspired by the xes event log standard (Acampora et al., 2017).

Dimensions		Categories & Subcategories				
Process Mining Type	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction Change Impact Execution Prediction	Action-oriented
Concept of interest	Control-Flow Execution Frequency Deviation Process Representation Dependency Variability Concept Drift Iterative Pattern	Time Cycle Time Bottlenecks Delays Pattern	Resources Value Utilization Assignment Interactions	Data Value Pattern	Costs	Unspecific
Primary Goal	Description Quantitative Qualitative	Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction	Prescription	
Purpose	Optimization		New Insight		Specific Information	
Context	Domain-Specific			Domain-Agnostic		
Data Level	Log	Trace	Event		Unspecific	

After classifying all questions of our collection (Question Collection 1 and 2) in this version of the taxonomy, we successfully confirmed all objective ending conditions, except for *Saturation* (D).

Despite this, all authors agreed that the current taxonomy likely satisfies the subjective ending conditions as well. To substantiate this belief, we conducted a preliminary evaluation with external stakeholders (see paper: Evaluation I, Sect. 3).

Involving experienced externals from the process mining research community and selected experts from industry helped us to gain an unbiased perspective. Indeed, Evaluation I revealed critical insights that we might have overlooked and that allowed us to improve the taxonomy further.

Acampora G, Vitiello A, Di Stefano B, van der Aalst W, Günther C, Verbeek E (2017) Ieee 1849: The xes standard. IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine pp 4–8

Gregor S (2006) The nature of theory in information systems. MIS quarterly pp 611–642

Nickerson R, Varshney U, Muntermann J (2013) A method for taxonomy development and its application in information systems. European Journal of Information Systems 22(3):336–359, 10.1057/ejis.2012.26

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 6 (C2E)

In iteration 6, we aimed to integrate the feedback of Evaluation I by undertaking another conceptual-to-empirical cycle (Nickerson et al., 2013), carefully considering the evaluation results. Our improvement efforts mainly focused on the dimension *Concept of interest*, as the evaluation revealed that several subcategories in this dimension could conceptually span several categories. Therefore, we reverted from the integration with the *Perspective* dimension and eliminated subcategories to enhance clarity and coherence.

Additionally, we observed that participants struggled to classify questions in the dimension *Process Mining Type*. To resolve this issue, we replaced it with the (business) *Goal* dimension, drawing on the categorization framework of process mining use case by Milani et al. (2022).

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories						
Goal	Transparency Discovery – Control Flow Rule Mining Resource involvement Change / Agility / Evolution		Performance Time Quality Cost		Compliance Business Rule Model Compliance		Automation
Perspective	Control-Flow	Time	Resources	Data	Costs	Unspecific	
Formulation	Description Quantitative Qualitative		Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction Change Impact Prediction Execution Prediction		Prescription
Query	Identify		Compare		Summarize		
Context	Domain-Specific			Domain-Agnostic			
Data Level	Log	Trace	Event	Unspecific			

For the assessment of the ending conditions of Version 6 of the taxonomy, we added further questions to our collection (cf. Question Collection 3, Sect. 3.1.3) and tested whether they could be classified in the taxonomy. We observed that all additional questions could be assigned to exactly one category or sub-category in each dimension. At the end of iteration 6, we therefore confirmed all objective ending conditions but *Saturation (D)*, as we changed dimensions and categories in this iteration. Additionally, all authors assessed the subjective ending conditions, carefully considering the results of Evaluation I. As a result, we deemed them satisfied.

Details on the Taxonomy Development Iterations

Design Iteration 7 (C2E) – Final Version

As *Saturation* (D) could not be reached in the previous iteration, we had to conduct at least one more conceptual-to-empirical development cycle (Nickerson et al., 2013). Similar to iteration 4, in this iteration, categories and sub-categories were reorganized through merging, renaming, promoting, and demoting (Kundisch et al., 2021).

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories						
Use Case	Transparency		Performance		Compliance		Automation
Perspective	Control-Flow	Time	Resources	Data	Costs	Unspecific	
Primary Goal	Describe <small>Quantitative</small> <small>Qualitative</small>		Confirm	Explain	Predict <small>Execution Prediction</small> <small>What-If Analysis</small>		Prescribe
Cognitive Step	Identification		Comparison			Summary	
Context	Domain-Specific			Domain-Agnostic			
Data Level	Log		Trace		Event		Unspecific

Further details on Taxonomy Version 7 can be found in the paper (cf. Sect. 4).

Following the recommendations of Kundisch et al. (2021), we conducted another evaluation (cf. Sect. 6) to confirm the usefulness of the taxonomy.

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

This questionnaire complements an interview to evaluate a newly developed process mining analysis question taxonomy.

All responses you provide for this study will be completely confidential. When the results of the study are reported, you will not be identified by name or any other information that could be used to infer your identity.

By clicking "Yes" below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood that:

- Your participation in this survey is voluntary.
- You may withdraw your consent and discontinue participation in the project at any time.
- Your refusal to participate will not in any way adversely impact upon you.
- You have given consent to be a subject of this research and respond to the survey / questionnaire(s) as truly as possible.

Thank you for participating in this research study!

Do you agree to participate in this interview?

Yes

No

Can you think of a question that you already asked or have been asked for a process analysis using process mining techniques?

You can either use a question that have already been posed to you as an analyst or a question you have read in the past. They might concern a specific domain/process.

Questions:

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

Process Mining Question Taxonomy

Leading Meta-Characteristic: Key Components of inquiries posed in the context of process mining analyses

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories					
Primary Goal What kind of answer is expected?	Description Quantitative Qualitative		Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction	Prescription
Concept of interest What is the main phenomenon that the question implies to analyze?	Control-Flow Execution Frequency Process Representation Deviation Dependency Variability Concept Drift Iterative- Pattern	Time Cycle Time Bottlenecks Delays Pattern	Resources Value Utilization Assignment Interactions	Data Value Pattern	Costs	Unspecific
Purpose What is the reason for asking the question?	Optimization		New Insight		Specific Information	
PM Type What type of PM analysis is required?	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction Change Impact Execution- Prediction	Action-oriented
Context Is the question bound to a specific context?	Domain-Specific			Domain-Agnostic		
Data Level What is the event log element that is investigated?	Log	Trace	Event	Unspecific		

Process Mining Question Taxonomy

Leading Meta-Characteristic: Key Components of inquiries posed in the context of process mining analyses

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories					
Primary Goal What kind of answer is expected?	Description Quantitative Qualitative		Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction	Prescription
Concept of interest What is the main phenomenon that the question implies to analyze?	Control-Flow Execution Frequency Process Representation Deviation Dependency Variability Concept Drift Iterative- Pattern	Time Cycle Time Bottlenecks Delays Pattern	Resources Value Utilization Assignment Interactions	Data Value Pattern	Costs	Unspecific
Purpose What is the reason for asking the question?	Optimization		New Insight		Specific Information	
PM Type What type of PM analysis is required?	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction Change Impact Execution- Prediction	Action-oriented
Context Is the question bound to a specific context?	Domain-Specific			Domain-Agnostic		
Data Level What is the event log element that is investigated?	Log	Trace	Event	Unspecific		

Is there anything that you would like to remark/suggest regarding the introduction of the taxonomy?

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

Let's look at a few examples:

What is the average throughput time for process Variant 2?

Dimensions	Categories & Subcategories				
Primary Goal What kind of answer is expected?	Description Quantitative Qualitative	Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction	Prescription
Concept of interest What is the main phenomenon that the question implies to analyze?	Control -Flow Execution Frequency Process Representation Deviation Dependency Variability Concept Drift Iterative Pattern	Time Bottleneck Delays Pattern	Resources Value Utilization Assignment Interactions	Data Value Pattern	Costs Unspecific
Purpose What is the reason for asking the question?	Optimization	New Insight	Specific Information		
PM Type What type of PM analysis is required?	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction Change Impact Execution Prediction Action-oriented
Context Is the question bound to a specific context?	Domain-Specific	Domain-Agnostic			
Data Level What is the event log element that is investigated?	Log	Trace	Event	Unspecific	

Is there anything that you would like to remark/suggest regarding the categorization of the example?

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

Let's look at a few examples:

What are the main root causes for orders being paid late?

Dimensions		Categories & Subcategories				
Primary Goal What kind of answer is expected?	Description Quantitative Qualitative	Confirmation	Explanation	Prediction	Prescription	
Concept of interest What is the main phenomenon that the question implies to analyze?	Control -Flow Execution Frequency Process Representation Deviation Dependency Variability Concept Drift Iterative Pattern	Time Cycle Time Synchronicity Delays Pattern	Resources Value Utilization Assignment Interactions	Data Value Pattern	Costs	Unspecific
Purpose What is the reason for asking the question?	Optimization	New Insight	Specific Information			
PM Type What type of PM analysis is required?	Discovery	Performance	Compliance	Comparison	Prediction Change Impact Execution Prediction	Action-oriented
Context Is the question bound to a specific context?	Domain-Specific	Domain-Agnostic				
Data Level What is the event log element that is investigated?	Log	Trace	Event	Unspecific		

Is there anything that you would like to remark/suggest regarding the categorization of the example?

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

For each question, the following questionnaire pages are displayed for the categorization.

- Option highlighted in blue expanded when selected.

question('AS01')

Dimension 1 – Primary Goal: What kind of answer is expected?

Please select a category.

Description

Confirmation

Explanation

Prediction

Prescription

I don't know

question('AS02')

Dimension 2 – Concept of Interest: What is the main phenomenon that needs to be analyzed?

Please select a category.

Control-Flow

Time

Resources

Data

Costs

Unspecific

I don't know

question('AS03')

Dimension 3 – Purpose: What is the reason for asking the question?

Please select a category.

Optimization

New Insight

Specific Information

I don't know

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

question('AS04')

Dimension 4 – Process Mining Type: What type of process mining analysis is required?

Please select a category.

- Discovery
 - Performance
 - Compliance
 - Comparison
 - Prediction
 - Action-oriented
-
- I don't know

question('AS05')

Dimension 5 – Context: Is the question bound to a specific context?

Please select a category.

- Domain-Specific
 - Domain-Agnostic
-
- I don't know

question('AS06')

Dimension 6 – Data Level: What is the event log element that is investigated?

Please select a category.

- Log
 - Trace
 - Event
 - Unspecific
-
- I don't know

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

To which extent to you agree to the following statements?

The taxonomy can successfully differentiate process mining analysis questions (Robustness).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy dimensions provide valuable information without being overwhelming (Conciseness).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy explains process mining analysis questions rather than only being descriptive (Explanatoriness).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy includes all dimensions and characteristics to classify all process mining analysis questions (Comprehensiveness).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

New dimensions and categories can easily be added to the taxonomy (Extensibility).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

To which extent to you agree to the following statements?

It is easy to apply the taxonomy to categorize questions.

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

It is useful to apply the taxonomy to categorize questions.

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy provides a good baseline to clarify questions (e.g., with stakeholders/process owners).

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy, together with a bank of categorized real-world process mining analysis questions, can support question identification.

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

The taxonomy, together with a bank of categorized real-world process mining analysis questions, can support question formulation.

Disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Fully agree
----------	--------------------	-----------------	-------------

Evaluation I - Questionnaire

Please indicate the following information

Your affiliation (i.e.,
academia vs.
industry):

Your current job role:

Years of experience in
process mining:

Approx. number of
answered or
formulated process
mining analysis
questions:

Years of experience in
the development of
concepts, such as
taxonomies, theories,
conceptual models,
or similar:

How do you rate your level of expertise in process mining?

[Please choose] ▼

How do you rate your level of expertise in the development of concepts, such as taxonomies, theories, conceptual models, or similar?

[Please choose] ▼

Evaluation I - Participant Details

ID	Job role	Process mining			Conceptual Design		Questions (own)
		# Years	Expertise	# Questions	# Years	Expertise	
P1	Assistant Professor	6-10	Good	50-100	1-5	Expert	1. What are the work-related interactions between resources? 2. How do people deviate from the agreed order of activities?
P2	Professor	11-15	Expert	50-100	1-5	Expert	
P3	Assistant Professor	6-10	Expert	101-500	1-5	Average	1. How does process behavior differ for different case groups?
P4	Teacher	1-5	Expert	50-100	11-20	Expert	1. What is the percentage of pull-requests that have been peer-reviewed? 2. Why are there 19% of cases unresolved?
P5	Assistant Professor	11-15	Expert	101-500	6-10	Good	1. How does the process look like?
P6	Professor	>15	Expert	>500	11-20	Expert	1. What is the process cycle time and where are passages of delay
P7	Professor	11-15	Expert	1-49	11-20	Expert	1. What are the reasons why the process takes longer than X in some cases? 2. What are the bottlenecks of the process?
P8	Consultant	1-5	Expert	101-500	0	Average	1. What is the level of automation in our procurement workflows?
P9	Professor	11-15	Expert	101-500	>20	Expert	
P10	Professor	11-15	Expert	101-500	1-5	Novice	1. Things go wrong in our process, can we pinpoint where the problem starts?
P11	Product Manager	1-5	Basic	0-49	1-5	Basic	1. What is my on time payment rate? 2. How many price changes do we have?
P13	Assistant Professor	1-5	Expert	50-100	1-5	Expert	1. What is the most striking thing about our process? 2. To what extent is our process unusual?
P14	Assistant professor	6-10	Expert	50-100	6-10	Expert	1. How does the process flow differ across different organizations?

Table 2: Participants of Evaluation I. Participants were asked to formulate their own process mining analysis questions at the beginning of each session (**Questions**). Additionally, the table lists the participant's **IDs**, their **Job role**, and, for the **field of process mining**, their number of years of experience in this field (**# Years**), their self-rated expertise (**Expertise**), and the approximate number of analysis questions (**# Questions**) they have already worked on themselves. Similarly, we also indicate the years of **experience in the design of concepts** (e.g., models, taxonomies) (**# Years**) and their self-rated **Expertise** in the same field.

The Process Mining Question Forge

For Evaluation II, we developed an approach for how to apply our question bank and taxonomy for designing new/own analysis question. The approach consists of 3 phases and can be applied in a workshop setting with a process mining project team. The approach is described in Sect. 6 in the paper.

Below, we show and describe how the three phases are implemented in a web application that participants could use during Evaluation II. We named the application *Process Mining Question Forge (PMQF)*.

Step 1 – Category Selection

In the first part, users are asked to reflect on their domain and a specific process they are interested in and identify the categories in each dimension that appear relevant to them. We consider this part as a sort of requirement identification.

Process Mining Question Forge Navigate ▾ Help ▾

PMQF - Question Design

Below, you are confronted with a list of categories and questions. Reflect on the questions and select the options that seem most relevant to you.

You can select multiple categories in case they are equally relevant to you.

You do not have to take a selection for each dimension. Feel free to skip dimensions, in case they are not relevant given your current situation. There might be questions that you cannot answer yet or for which you do not want to take a selection.

1. Use Case

Process mining analyses serves different goals and can therefore be differentiated according to the use case that you aim to realize. **Which of the following process mining use cases best aligns with your business interest?** Select one, multiple, or none.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transparency	<input type="checkbox"/> Performance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compliance Assessing or improving process compliance with legal or internal regulations (e.g., to-be models, business rules).	<input type="checkbox"/> Automation
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2. Perspective

Processes can be analyzed from different perspectives as event logs are typically enriched with information such as resources, costs, or other attributes. **Are there specific perspectives that you are interested in?** Select one, multiple, or none.

<input type="checkbox"/> Control-Flow	<input type="checkbox"/> Time	<input type="checkbox"/> Data	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources	<input type="checkbox"/> Costs
---------------------------------------	-------------------------------	-------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------------

3. Primary Goal

Depending on how a question is formulated (e.g., which question word is used) the answer you can expect may vary. **Which activity best describes the type of response you are looking for?** Select one, multiple, or none.

<input type="checkbox"/> Describe	<input type="checkbox"/> Confirm	<input type="checkbox"/> Explain	<input type="checkbox"/> Predict	<input type="checkbox"/> Prescribe
-----------------------------------	----------------------------------	----------------------------------	----------------------------------	------------------------------------

4. Cognitive Step

Do you already know whether information needs to be identified, compared (with each other or with an external benchmark) or summarized? The answer to this question might depend on the cardinality ("magnitude") of the data elements you expect as output. Are you interested in the list of outputs (e.g., a list of vendors), a comparison of outputs (e.g., a ranking of vendors), or a summary of the output (e.g., count of all vendors involved)? Select one, multiple, or none.

<input type="checkbox"/> Identify	<input type="checkbox"/> Compare	<input type="checkbox"/> Summarize
-----------------------------------	----------------------------------	------------------------------------

5. Data Level

The data on which a process analysis is based is usually provided in the form of event logs (also known as activity tables). In this context, questions could aim at the entire data set, as well as at the analysis of subsets of traces, or subsets of events. **Which of the following groups of data elements are you interested in?** Select one, multiple, or none.

<input type="checkbox"/> Log	<input type="checkbox"/> Trace	<input type="checkbox"/> Event
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The Process Mining Question Forge

Step 2 – Question Filter

In the second part, the selection of categories is used as a filter on the question bank, and questions relevant to the user's need are returned. We acknowledge that not all questions from this result will be relevant. Therefore, in this part, questions can be reviewed and only those that appear relevant to the setting of the users should be selected for the last part.

Process Mining Question Forge [Navigate](#) [Help](#)

Questions

The following list of questions matches your selection and can provide some inspiration for your own question design. It consists of questions that are domain-specific and domain-agnostic. Domain-agnostic questions might be easier to be adopted to your own use cases, while domain-specific questions are questions that have been raised for very specific processes. From the list below, select those questions that appear relevant to you and save them for the next refinement step.

Selected categories:

- Use Case: Compliance, and Transparency
- Perspective: Time

Number of questions matching the selection: 15

What is the average period to return to a steady state after a change in terms of number of closed interactions and incidents?

Source: BPIC 2014

Context: Domain-specific; Use Case: Transparency; Perspective: Time; Primary Goal: Describe; Quantitative; Cognitive Step: Summarize; Data Level: Unspecific

Is there evidence that cases are pushed to the 2nd and 3rd service line too soon?

Source: BPIC 2013

Context: Domain-specific; Use Case: Compliance; Perspective: Time; Primary Goal: Confirm; Cognitive Step: Identify; Data Level: Event

Is the "wait user" substatus abused to hide problems with the total resolution time?

Source: BPIC 2013

Context: Domain-specific; Use Case: Compliance; Perspective: Time; Primary Goal: Confirm; Cognitive Step: Identify; Data Level: Event

Save selected questions

View selected questions

Filter results by remaining dimensions:

Context:

All

Primary Goal:

All

Cognitive Step:

All

Data Level:

All

The Process Mining Question Forge

Step 3 – Question Refinement

In the third part, the final set of (relevant) questions is determined. Selected questions can be reformulated or ultimately excluded, in cases where the reformulation fails. The remaining set of questions is the result of the question design approach and can be utilized as input for a process mining analysis.

Results - Selected Questions

Below you can find the overview of questions you selected so far. The heatmap indicates the categories that your questions cover. Below, you can inspect your questions in detail and reformulate them according to your domain.

Number of questions selected: 2

Question Analytics

Selected Questions

What is the average period to return to a steady state after a change in terms of number of closed interactions and incidents?

Source: BPIC 2014; Context: Domain-specific; Data Level: Unspecific

Reformulation (if required)

Remove Question

Is the "wait user" substatus abused to hide problems with the total resolution time?

Source: BPIC 2013; Context: Domain-specific; Data Level: Event

Reformulation (if required)

Remove Question

Submit All Reformulations

Back to category selection

Export to CSV

Evaluation II - Evaluation Guide

The goal of Evaluation II was to evaluate the applicability and usefulness of the taxonomy and question bank in real-world settings. We therefore designed an evaluative case study that allowed us to organize and perform workshops with process mining stakeholders in their organizational context.

Guide for Moderator(s) (Author) (1/2)

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Welcome participants and introduce the purpose of the session:
 - Evaluating the (perceived) usefulness of the PMQF tool for question design.
 - Supporting participants to identify questions for their own purpose.
- Show/Explain Agenda
 - Introduction
 - Introduce the tool
 - Understand participant's situations
 - Working Session
 - Participants should use the tool – Ideally, one of them shares and moderator walks them through the question selection together
 - [Goal: Try to identify at least 15-20 questions that gave you new ideas or that could be directly applied to your situation]
 - Discussion, Feedback & Questionnaire

2. Tool Introduction (10-15 minutes)

- PMQF stands for Process Mining Question Forge (German: Schmiede). It builds on top of a catalog of process analysis questions (>400) and a taxonomy that was developed to allow the categorization of analysis questions along 6 dimensions
- [Open the tool and share the taxonomy via “View Taxonomy”]
- Walk the participants through the different dimensions and the examples
- Provide an overview of the remaining PMQF functions on a high level
- Allow participants to ask questions for clarification.

3. Understanding the situation of participants (5-10 minutes)

- Ensure that the moderator understands the situation, goals, and challenges that participants currently face when using process mining in their organizational setting. Questions:
 - What is your previous experience with conducting process mining projects in the organization?
 - Let participants rate the maturity level of process mining in their organization if not done already (see consent form)
 - In the past, did you already consider (clear) questions for your projects?
 - Is there any ongoing project / a specific implementation that you are working on now and for which you want to design analysis questions? Please explain.

Evaluation II - Evaluation Guide

The goal of Evaluation II was to evaluate the applicability and usefulness of the taxonomy and question bank in real-world settings. We therefore designed an evaluative case study that allowed us to organize and perform workshops with process mining stakeholders in their organizational context.

Guide for Moderator(s) (Author) (2/2)

4. Workshop (45-120 min)

- Given a small group 2-5 participants, groups will not be split.
- Task: Try to identify at ~15-20 questions that give you new ideas or that are relevant for your situation
- One of the participants should volunteer to share the screen. Discuss selections together and clarify questions (i.e., when dimensions or categories are not clear anymore and participants struggle with the navigation)
- Do not comment or evaluate the selection of questions - this part should be up to the participants.
 - Moderator can guide the participants, give examples & show them how they can save questions and iterate back to take new selections

5. Interview/Discussion (15 -30 min)

- Questions:
 - Can you describe your first impression of the PMQF tool?
 - How relevant do you find the PMQF tool in addressing your situation?
 - Were there any features that you found particularly helpful or lacking in this context?
 - Are there any improvements or additional features that you can suggest?

6. Questionnaire (15 min)

Evaluation II - Questionnaire

This questionnaire complements a workshop conducted to evaluate the PMQF tool.

All responses you provide for this study will be completely confidential. When the results of the study are reported, you will not be identified by name or any other information that could be used to infer your identity.

By clicking "Yes" below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood that:

- Your participation in this survey is voluntary.
- You may withdraw your consent and discontinue participation in the project at any time. Your refusal to participate will not in any way adversely impact upon you.
- You have given consent to be a subject of this research and respond to the survey / questionnaire(s) as truly as possible.

Thank you for participating in this research study!

Do you agree?

Yes

No

During the previous workshop, you used PMQF to develop questions for process analysis.

1. What was your goal in using the tool and follow the guided question design?

Please select all that apply.

I had no particular goal.

To get inspiration for new questions for a specific process mining

To get an idea of what kind of questions I could ask for process mining projects in general.

To identify specific questions that are relevant to my current situation (e.g. current project, ongoing

To identify specific questions that could become relevant for me in the future (e.g. for a project planned in the next 6 months).

Other:

Further:

2. Were you able to achieve your goal during the workshop with the help of PMQF?

[Please choose] ▼

Evaluation II - Questionnaire

How likely do the following statements apply to you?

	Extremely Likely	Quite Likely	Slightly Likely	Neither	Slightly Unlikely	Quite Unlikely	Extremely Unlikely
Using PMQF would enable me to accomplish the design of analysis question more quickly.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using PMQF would improve my performance in designing analysis questions.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using PMQF would increase my productivity in designing analysis questions.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using PMQF would enhance my effectiveness in PM project planning and question design.	<input type="radio"/>						
Using PMQF would make it easier to design PM analysis questions.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find PMQF useful for designing PM analysis questions.	<input type="radio"/>						

How likely do the following statements apply to you?

	Extremely Likely	Quite Likely	Slightly Likely	Neither	Slightly Unlikely	Quite Unlikely	Extremely Unlikely
Learning to operate PMQF would be easy for me.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find it easy to get PMQF do what I want it to do.	<input type="radio"/>						
My interaction with PMQF would be clear and understandable.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find PMQF to be flexible to interact with.	<input type="radio"/>						
It would be easy for me to become skillful at using PMQF.	<input type="radio"/>						
I would find PMQF easy to use.	<input type="radio"/>						

To which extent to you agree with the following statement?

	Fully agree	Partially agree	Partially disagree	Fully disagree
PMQF can support the design (identification) of analysis questions in process mining projects.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Evaluation II - Questionnaire

Next, the questionnaire involved the following questions for each dimension of the taxonomy:

Page 04

Dim1

Next, we will ask you to shortly reflect on the dimensions that are used in PMQF to differentiate questions.

1. Context

The Context dimension captures whether the question (as it is formulated) is related to a specific domain or context.

Categories: Domain-specific, Domain-agnostic

To which extent to you agree to the following statements?

	Fully Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Fully Disagree
I understand the dimension.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I understand the categories.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The dimension is useful to design or identify questions for a process mining analysis (no clear question in mind).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The dimension is useful to classify process mining analysis questions (given a question).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If you do not fully agree with the statements, can you indicate which parts are not understandable? If possible, add a brief explanation.

Is there any further feedback you can share for the Context dimension?

The questions were repeated for Context, Use Case, Perspective, Primary Goal, Cognitive Step, and Data Level.

Evaluation II - Questionnaire

Last but not least, we have a few questions about your position and experience.

What is your current job role?

How many years of experience do you have in process mining?

Briefly explain your involvement/role in previous process mining projects (e.g., worked as analyst, supervised projects, evaluated analysis outcomes, etc.)

Approx. number of process mining analysis questions answered or formulated. A rough estimate is sufficient (consider all process mining projects/analyses you have been involved in over the past few years. Were there 0, 5 or 10 questions or is the number closer to 50 or 100?)

Did you already experience difficulties with the design of analysis questions in the past?

How do you rate your level of expertise in process mining?

[Please choose] ▾

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Welcome to the Survey!

Thank you for considering taking part in this study. This survey is intended primarily for students (Bachelor, Master, or PhD) with a basic understanding of process mining—for example, if you have taken one or more courses where process mining was introduced or discussed.

Please note:

- If you have never heard of process mining, or if you already have practical experience and consider yourself an expert (e.g., through participating in a real-world process mining project outside of an academic context), we kindly ask that you do not participate in this study.

If these criteria apply to you, your participation is greatly valued and will contribute to academic research. All responses will remain completely anonymous, and no identifying information will be collected.

As a token of appreciation, participants who complete the survey and follow the guidelines will have the chance to win an Amazon or Galaxus voucher (1x 50 €/CHF, 2x 25 €/CHF). At the end of the survey, you'll have the option to enter your email address to participate in the raffle. Your email will be stored separately from your responses to ensure complete anonymity.

Important guidelines:

- Ensure that you have around 1 hour for taking enough time to answer the questions and complete the tasks of the study thoroughly. However, you might be faster than that.
- During the survey, you will need to watch some videos explaining important concepts. Be prepared to play the videos (e.g. in a quiet environment or with headphones).
- Answer the questions independently, without consulting external sources such as search engines, reference materials, or generative AI tools.
- You are not being evaluated on your answers. The goal is to understand your own perspectives and ideas, so we encourage you to respond honestly and thoughtfully.

By proceeding, you confirm that you have understood these instructions and agree to participate. Thank you for your time and effort, and good luck in the raffle!

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

1. Which country do you live in?

2. What best describes your current profession?

Please insert the industry you are working in, in case it is not academia.

Bachelor Student

Master Student

PhD Student

Postdoctoral researcher

Employed in a different industry:

Employer in a different industry:

3. In case you are a student, which study program are you enrolled in?

Type "None", in case you are not enrolled in any program.

4. If you have already learned about process mining in one or more courses as part of your studies, list the names of these courses.

Please, separate course names with a semicolon.

5. Can you (briefly) describe your experience in process mining?

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

6. How would you rate your level of expertise in process mining?

- Expert
- Advanced
- Good
- Basic
- Novice

7. Approximately how many hours have you spent learning about process mining?

- Less than 5 hours
- 5-10 hours
- 10-20 hours
- 20-50 hours
- 50-100 hours
- More than 100 hours

8. Which of the following process mining tools/frameworks have you already used, even if it was only for a short period of time?

- Celonis
- ProM
- Disco
- Apromore
- SAP Signavio
- PM4PY
- BupaR

Any other tools (please specify):

None

9. During this study, we will present a scenario from a manufacturing company that produces and distributes trucks. Without further information and based on your initial feeling, how would you rate your level of expertise in this domain?

- Expert
- Advanced
- Good
- Basic
- Novice

10. Please describe your experience with this domain in one sentence.

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Thank you for answering the initial questions! Soon, you will step into the role of a process mining analyst.

Before we move on, please watch the following video to gain a general understanding of what a process mining project looks like in practice. This will help set the stage for the upcoming scenario.

Welcome to this short introduction to process mining!

Before continuing with the questionnaire, let's take a moment to explore what process mining is and how it works in practice. This will give you a solid foundation for what's to come.

So, what is process mining? At its core, process mining helps us uncover and analyze real-world processes. These processes could be anything, from manufacturing a car to treating a patient in a hospital or ordering clothes online.

When processes happen, they leave digital footprints in various information systems. These traces, known as event data, are the foundation of process mining.

For example, in a company, a sales order might be logged in a Customer Relationship Management tool (short: CRM), and processed further in another system, so that the event data for the complete process is stored in different databases.

To reconstruct a process, we gather and transform these digital traces into a format called an event log. An event log captures three key things: what happened, who or what was involved, and when it happened. Additional details, like the resource responsible or the cost of an item, can also be included if relevant to the analysis.

Once the event log is ready, we can start analyzing. With process discovery, we create visual representations that show how processes really unfold, including paths, frequencies, and skipped steps. Performance analysis helps us identify delays and inefficiencies. Conformance checking allows us to compare the real process against rules or guidelines. Process mining can also help with predictions, such as forecasting outcomes or estimating how long a process will take.

So, how does a typical process mining project work? It usually starts with a research question. For example, if you are interested in performance, you might ask, "How can we reduce delays in the process?" Once the goal is clear, the next step is to collect – and prepare the data. This involves identifying where the data is stored, extracting it, and formatting it into an event log.

With the event log in hand, the project moves into the analysis phase. Here, process mining techniques are applied to uncover insights that align with the project goals.

Finally, the results are shared with stakeholders, discussions are held, and improvements might be implemented based on the findings.

For this survey, we will focus on the first phase of a process mining project—the planning phase.

Now that you've seen what process mining is about and how projects typically work, you're ready to dive into the initial planning process.

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Only presented to Test Group

In the following page, you will be presented with a realistic process mining project scenario. Your task is to identify three relevant analysis questions based on the provided process description.

To support you in this ideation process, you will have access to a taxonomy and a collection of process mining analysis questions, which you can use as inspiration. Below, you will find a link to a website where both resources are available. Please open it now in a new tab.

Before using the tool, please watch the introductory video below. If you have any questions or encounter any difficulties while using the tool, feel free to reach out to us at any time via email: lisa.zimmermann@unisg.ch.

[Click here to access the Website](#)

Hi there, and welcome to this introduction video!

To help you identify relevant questions for the process mining project you'll be working on in the next step, you have access to a web-based tool. This tool is built around a categorization scheme—or taxonomy—and includes a collection of over 400 real-world process mining analysis questions.

When you open the tool, your first step is to navigate to the **Question Design** feature. You can get there using the navigation bar or by clicking the button on the main page.

Once you're in, the tool will guide you through five categories. For each category, you'll be able to select answers that match what you're interested in. For example, the first category focuses on use cases for process mining. You'll be asked if any of the listed use cases align with your business goals. If you hover over an option, you'll see a brief description to help you decide.

You can select one, multiple, or even none of the options—whatever feels right for you. If you're unsure or want to keep your options open, it's fine to select nothing. To show you how this works, I'll make some random choices. For the use cases, I'll select **Transparency** and **Performance**. I'll focus on the **Time** and **Resource Perspectives**, include all **Primary Goals**, **Cognitive Steps**, and the **Data Level**.

When it's your turn, take your time to go through all five categories and make selections based on your preferences.

After you've made your selections, click **Submit**. The tool will then show you a list of questions from our collection that match your criteria. In my example, 140 questions are displayed. However, it is possible that, based on your initial category selections, no questions match your criteria. If that happens, try expanding your options and testing the filters again.

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Only presented to Test Group

In the following page, you will be presented with a realistic process mining project scenario. Your task is to identify three relevant analysis questions based on the provided process description.

To support you in this ideation process, you will have access to a taxonomy and a collection of process mining analysis questions, which you can use as inspiration. Below, you will find a link to a website where both resources are available. Please open it now in a new tab.

Before using the tool, please watch the introductory video below. If you have any questions or encounter any difficulties while using the tool, feel free to reach out to us at any time via email: lisa.zimmermann@unisg.ch.

[Click here to access the Website](#)

[Continued from previous page] On the right-hand side, you'll see additional filtering options for all dimensions you haven't narrowed down yet. Keep in mind that these filters won't change the number that is displayed at the top of the page, but they'll be applied to the list and can be changed on the fly.

Most of the questions you see might be domain-specific and won't directly match the process scenario you'll work on. But that's okay! Use them as inspiration and select questions that you think could be relevant or have some interesting aspects.

Once you're done selecting questions, save your work. You can either adjust your initial category selections or review the questions you've saved so far.

On the **final page**, you'll see all your selected questions. Here, you can remove those that no longer seem relevant or rewrite them to better suit your specific scenario. Don't forget to save your changes! When you're happy with your final list, you can export it or go back to explore more categories.

For this study, you'll need to identify exactly **three relevant questions**. If you've saved more than three, pick the ones you feel are the most meaningful and relevant for the given context.

One final note: **please only use this tool for the survey**. Don't refer to any other sources like search engines or generative AI tools. Even if you already have ideas in mind, engage with the tool to see if it sparks new insights or adds value to your current thoughts.

Feel free to switch between the tool and the survey as you jot down notes or finalize your list of questions.

And lastly, if you're short on time, we recommend spending no more than 30 minutes using the tool to identify your questions.

Thanks for watching, and good luck with the survey!

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Task:

You just started a new job as a process mining analyst at MyTruck, a Swiss-based company that manufactures industrial vehicles (such as trucks) in Europe. Like many manufacturers, MyTruck faces challenges in the current economic situation. While excelling in e-Truck (electrified) production, the main revenue is still made with regular-engine trucks (mainly diesel). The company is investigating its diesel engine manufacturing process to identify potential improvements for any form of cost reduction or improved productivity in this process.

As part of this initiative, you have full access to a process mining tool, in which the diesel engine manufacturing process data is fully integrated. You can find a more detailed description of the process and the event log scheme further down on this page.

Unfortunately, manufacturing is a domain where process mining has been less widely applied, and in the past, external consultants have provided limited guidance on uncovering meaningful use cases and generating actionable insights. Therefore, you are asked to resume the project.

As a good process mining analyst, you know that it is best practice to start any process mining initiative from a planning phase, in which concrete analysis questions are formulated and aligned with all project stakeholders.

It is your task to develop a set of relevant and impactful questions to guide your analysis. Those questions should go beyond describing control-flow — such as the order of events implied by the question *"How does the process look like?"* — and time — such as the throughput time of the complete or sub-processes implied by the question *"How long does the process take?"*. These aspects have already been explored. Instead, focus on questions that address other dimensions of the process, go beyond descriptions (e.g., explanatory questions), reveal valuable insights, and align with the company's broader goals.

11. Now we ask you to work in the role of a process mining analyst, considering the information above. What are three meaningful questions you would raise for the project?

Feel free to take notes or gather your ideas in the field below, before you formulate your final questions!

Below you will find space for personal notes and further information about the process, including a detailed process description and an overview of the event log scheme.

12. Here, you can take some notes or gather ideas, before you formulate your final questions in the text above. This field will not be analyzed/considered. Feel free to use it for your notes.

--

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Process Description:

The diesel engine assembly process at MyTruck is a complex series of activities designed to produce high-quality engines efficiently. It begins with **material preparation**, where raw materials and components, such as cylinders and pistons, are **sourced and inspected**. The process then moves into the **initial assembly**, where core components like the **cylinder block** are **aligned and fitted together**, ensuring a solid foundation for subsequent steps.

In the **intermediate assembly** stage, subassemblies such as **crankshafts and connecting rods** are **installed**, with a focus on precision and alignment. During this stage, a **manual quality control step** is conducted to inspect the assembly of critical components, ensuring accuracy before proceeding. Following this, the engine undergoes a **painting step**, where **protective coatings** are applied to enhance durability and corrosion resistance. Once painted, the engine continues to the **final assembly stage**, where systems such as the **fuel and cooling systems** are **integrated**.

Before the process is completed, an **automated quality control step** utilizes advanced sensors and testing equipment to **verify the integrity and performance**. The engines undergo rigorous performance testing to evaluate metrics like fuel efficiency, emissions, and operational reliability. If any issues are identified, a rework phase addresses defects to ensure the final product meets quality standards.

Event Log Scheme

Column Name	Description	Example Values
Case ID	A unique identifier for each process instance.	Engine_001, Engine_002, Engine_003
Activity	The name of the activity or event in the process.	Assemble Cylinder, Quality Check 02, Painting
Timestamp	The date and time when the activity was performed.	2024-12-04 08:15:00
Machine	The machine that was in use for performing the activity (if applicable).	Station_01, Station_02, Machine_23
Resource	The worker responsible for performing an activity (if applicable).	Worker_01, Robot_324
Activity Type	A classification of the activity	Manual, Automated, Inspection
Production Batch	The identifier for the production batch to which the instance belongs.	Batch_12A, Batch_12B
Order ID	The identifier for the customer order associated with the case (if applicable).	Order_1234, Order_19993424
Energy Usage	The amount of energy consumed by the machine/resource during the activity.	12 kWh, 15 kWh
Material Type	The material that is used during the assembly step.	Screws, BlackPaint, Cylinder_A23H, NA

Example

Case ID	Activity	Timestamp	Machine	Resource	Activity Type	Production Batch	Order ID	Energy Usage	Material Type
Engine_001	Source material	04.12.2024 08:15	Station_01	Worker_01	Manual	Batch_12B	Order_1234	-	Screws
Engine_001	Source material	04.12.2024 08:16	Station_01	Worker_01	Manual	Batch_12B	Order_1234	-	Pipe
Engine_001	Source material	04.12.2024 08:17	Station_01	Worker_01	Manual	Batch_12B	Order_1234	-	Cylinder
Engine_001	Inspect materials	04.12.2024 08:25	-	Worker_01	Inspection	Batch_12B	Order_1234	-	-
Engine_001	Assemble cylinder block	04.12.2024 10:14	Station_01	Worker_02	Manual	Batch_12B	Order_1234	-	-
Engine_001	Install rods	04.12.2024 10:34	Machine_23	Robot_324	Automated	Batch_12B	Order_1234	15 kWh	-
...
Engine_3425	Painting	08.12.2024 16:14	Machine_P2	Robot_P2	Automated	Batch_453	Order_452	10 kWh	Paint
...

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to brainstorm meaningful analysis questions in your role as a process analyst for MyTruck! Below, we will ask you a few concluding questions about your satisfaction with the result and recommendations for further improvements! Please answer the questions intuitively.

13. How satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the quality of your questions?

very
dissatisfied very satisfied

14. To what extent do the questions reflect the requirements of the task?

not at all to a very great
extent

15. To what extent do you feel committed to the questions you formulated?

not at all to a very great
extent

16. To what extent are you confident that the questions are correct?

not at all to a very great
extent

Only presented to Test Group

question("QU12")

17. To what extent are the three questions you have formulated inspired by questions you have identified in the question tool?

not at all to a very great
extent (direct
copies of
questions from
the tool)

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

Only presented to Test Group

question("QU13")

18. I found the taxonomy and question bank useful for generating meaningful questions.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

19. My process of question generation was

inefficient efficient

uncoordinated coordinated

confusing understandable

dissatisfying satisfying

question("QU07")

Only presented to Test Group

20. To which extent do you agree to the following statements?

I think that I would like to use the taxonomy frequently.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I found the taxonomy unnecessarily complex.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I thought the taxonomy was easy to use.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I think that I would need the support of a technical expert to use this taxonomy successfully.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I found the various components of the taxonomy well-integrated and consistent.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I thought there was too much inconsistency in the taxonomy.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I imagine that most people would learn to use this taxonomy very quickly.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I found the taxonomy cumbersome to use.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I felt confident using the taxonomy.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the taxonomy.

Fully disagree Partially disagree Neither Partially agree Fully agree

Evaluation III - Questionnaire

question('QU10')

22. Is there anything else you can share regarding the question ideation process? For example, did you experience any other issues, not connected to the taxonomy?

question('QU11')

23. In case you experienced any issues while brainstorming meaningful questions, can you briefly describe what you struggled with and why?

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E-Mail

24. Did you visit any kind of AI-based systems or websites while filling out the questionnaire (e.g. ChatGPT)?

Yes

No

25. If you would like to participate in the raffle, please enter your e-mail address so that we can inform you in case you won!

E-mail:

Last Page

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

Evaluation III - Participant Details

ID	Group	Nationality	Degree	Study Program	Process Mining			Manufacturing
					Expertise	Practice (Hours)	Tools	Expertise
S1	Test	Switzerland	Bachelor	Computer Science	Basic	20-50	Celonis, Disco, PM4PY	Novice
S2	Test	Germany	Bachelor	Information Systems	Basic	< 5	None	Novice
S3	Test	Germany	Bachelor	Information Systems	Basic	10-20	Signavio	Basic
S4	Test	Austria	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S5	Test	Germany	Master	Information Systems	Basic	5-10	Celonis, Signavio	Good
S6	Test	Germany	Bachelor	Computer Science	Basic	5-10	None	Basic
S7	Test	Austria	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S8	Test	Austria	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S9	Test	Austria	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S10	Test	Austria	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S11	Test	Liechtenstein	Bachelor	Business Administration	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S12	Test	Germany	Bachelor	Computer Science	Basic	5-10	Celonis	Novice
S13	Test	Netherlands	Bachelor	Data Science and AI	Good	50-100	ProM, Disco, PM4PY	Novice
S14	Test	Netherlands	PhD	Computer Science	Good	20-50	ProM, PM4PY	Basic
S15	Test	Netherlands	PhD	NA	Good	>100	ProM, Disco, PM4PY	Basic
S16	Test	Switzerland	Master	NA	Good	>100	Celonis, ProM, Disco, Signavio, PM4PY	Basic
S17	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Business Informatics	Good	10-20	Celonis, Signavio	Advanced
S18	Control	Germany	Bachelor	NA	Novice	< 5	None	Basic
S19	Control	Germany	PhD	Business Informatics	Basic	< 5	None	Novice
S20	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Computer Science	Good	20-50	None	Good
S21	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Business Informatics	Novice	< 5	Celonis	Novice
S22	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Information Systems	Basic	5-10	Celonis, Signavio	Novice
S23	Control	Germany	Bachelor	NA	Novice	< 5	Signavio	Novice
S24	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Computer Science	Basic	< 5	Celonis	Novice
S25	Control	Germany	Bachelor	Information Systems	Basic	10-20	Celonis, Signavio	Novice
S26	Control	Netherlands	Bachelor	Data Science and AI	Good	>100	ProM, PM4PY	Novice
S27	Control	Netherlands	Postdoc	NA	Basic	5-10	ProM	Novice
S28	Control	Spain	Bachelor	Software Engineering	Good	20-50	PM4PY	Basic
S29	Control	Netherlands	PhD	NA	Novice	10-20	ProM, Disco	Novice
S30	Control	Switzerland	Bachelor	Computer Science	Novice	< 5	None	Novice
S31	Control	Switzerland	PhD	Computer Science	Novice	< 5	None	Novice

Table 3: Participants of Evaluation III, listing student IDs (not in order of data collection), their assigned Groups, Nationality, the qualifications they are currently pursuing (Degree) and their Study Program. Additionally, we asked students to indicate their level of Expertise in process mining, the hours they have spent practicing it (Practice), and the Tools they have already seen. As we asked them to design analysis questions for a manufacturing process, we also asked them for their Expertise for this domain.

Discussion – ChatGPT Prompt

```
question_domain = "The incident and problem management
process."

target_domain = "A manufacturing process, in which truck
engines are assembled."

question = "Is there evidence that cases are pushed to
the 2nd and 3rd service line too soon?"

messages=[
  {
    "role": "system",
    "content": "You are a process mining expert
able to support the planning phase of
process mining projects, in which the goal is
to formulate relevant questions for the
analysis."
  },
  {
    "role": "user",
    "content": "I will provide you with a process
mining analysis question. It was formulated
for" + question_domain + "However, I am
responsible for" + target_domain + "Please
assess how the question could be reformulated
for my context." + question
  }
]
```